

CHEMICAL INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT TREND MODELING AND FORECASTING

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Annotation. *The article analyzes the relationship between the development strategy of the chemical complex industry and other production sectors. In addition, proposals for the development of the competitive position of the chemical industry in the production industry and the role of the chemical industry in the economy of our country, as well as short-term forecast values, are presented.*

Keywords: *Institutional models, competitiveness, mineral fertilizer, diversification, petrochemical, production capacity.*

Introduction

Competitiveness in the world market and successful development of the country in modern conditions with the updated system of problems in the world economic space requires updated approaches in the formation and implementation of the industrial policy of the state. The current stage of the development of globalization processes and market changes in the industrial sector of the national economy requires the development of qualitative approaches to the management of the industrial sector. Solving the problems of institutional organization of the operation of the industrial system is relevant for the industrial policy of any country.

Institutional models make it possible to account for differences in the institutional conditions of different countries. Thus, in particular, two important situations should be taken into account when forming the innovation policy of a developing country. The first of them is that the main role in the innovation process of these countries is played by the public sector, not the private one; the second is in the specific features of the interpretation of innovations. For these countries,

innovation does not mean expanding the technological frontier and creating advanced technologies, but the absorption, diffusion and diffusion of existing technologies.

Based on the decision of the head of our state on August 23, 2017, the chemical industry development program for 2017-2021 was adopted. In it, 43 investment projects with a total value of 3.1 billion dollars were implemented, increasing the volume of industrial products by 2.4 times, exports by 2.7 times, increasing the share of localized products to 42.5 percent, and mastering the production of 43 new types of products. , it is planned to create more than 3,200 new jobs. In order to regulate the export-import activity of the network, to ensure the transparency of foreign trade processes, most importantly, to increase the volume of sales of chemical products in foreign markets and to expand its geography, to ensure further increase in competitiveness and attractiveness, the limited liability company "Uzkimyoimpeks" was established. done.

Of course, the large-scale reforms that are being implemented are also giving positive results in the chemical industry. But the systemic problems that have persisted in the network for many years have not yet been resolved. For example, industrial enterprises producing mineral fertilizers are in a difficult financial situation.

The lack of attention to the financing of agriculture or a superficial approach to the issue is causing defects in the system of mutual settlements in this area, the President said.

Costs related to mineral fertilizers used in agriculture are not covered. As a result, the ability of chemical enterprises to make payments for natural gas, electricity, phosphorite raw materials, sulfuric acid and other types of goods and services used for production is limited, and creditor debt is growing.

Research methodology

Several studies have been conducted on modeling and forecasting of industrial production processes, multidimensional optimization of production, regional development of the chemical industry and the classification of its multidimensional dynamics.

The main directions of development and diversification of the chemical industry are as follows:

- expanding the nomenclature of products with high added value based on deep processing of hydrocarbon raw materials and mineral resources;
- creation and modernization of new production facilities;
- to reduce the participation of the state in the authorized capital of chemical industry enterprises, to attract direct investments in the industry, to develop cooperative relations between industrial enterprises and business entities;
- active development of science and branch scientific research, integration of advanced developments into production;
- to improve the quality of design and engineering work and diagnostic research, to organize an effective system of personnel training and retraining.

The following factors play a role in the competitive situation of the chemical industry:

- increase in world prices of chemical products due to growth;
- Expansion of demand for chemical and petrochemical products (domestic market, first of all, construction, industrial and household sector);
- decrease in the competitiveness of local prices, inflation, increase in the price of goods and services;
- Inadequate effective demand in the domestic market, the chemical complex of consumers of mineral fertilizers, which forms the basis of export (30-35 percent of foreign exchange earnings);
- lowering the level of protection of local producers due to the negative impact of imports.

The strategy for the development of the chemical complex industry is designed for:

- determining the priorities for the development of the chemical complex;
- development of the chemical complex, which is the conceptual basis of public-private partnership;
- ensuring coordination of actions of executive authorities;
- development of targeted programs for the development of the chemical complex;

Implementation of strategy rules helps to:

- creating long-term conditions for sustainable development of chemical complex enterprises and increasing their competitiveness in world markets in open economy conditions
- elimination of the technological backwardness of the chemical complex
- ensuring economic, defense and environmental security

Analysis and results

Any modern branch of industry cannot do without petrochemical and chemical segment products. It should be noted that domestic chemical products are exported to more than 30 countries. Today, this branch of Uzbekistan ranks 8th in the world in nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium production.

Figure 1. Microeconomic indicators

In accordance with the changes in macroeconomic indicators, strategies and prospects for the development of related sectors and sectors of the economy (industry, transport, construction industry, housing, communal and agricultural, energy, industrial complex, social sector) are predicted, and thus internal market opportunities are significantly increased. In particular, prices will increase to 2,410 billion in 2019, and to 4,860 billion in 2024.

As the main factor stopping the development of the industry, the chemical industry should primarily include:

- high physical and mental wear and tear production capacity;
- high-quality equipment of basic technology;
- use of outdated technology; equipment and their low performance;
- high energy and material consumption of production;

Conclusions and suggestions

In addition, it is necessary to diversify production for a more stable development of the chemical industry of Uzbekistan. The course of rapid modernization of the economy adopted by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan implies a radical change in the role and importance of the chemical industry in the development of industrial production and its contribution to the country's Gross Domestic Product. Diversification of production helps to solve this problem, which is a measure to improve the product composition of production based on increasing the level of processing of raw materials relative to the chemical complex, developing infrastructure, changing logistics connections, eliminating monopolization of production, and improving the management strategy. Includes implementation of activities.

Taking into account the above, there is a great need to eliminate the listed problems in the industry, which is the main segment of the industry, which has a great impact not only on the structural changes in the economy, but also on ensuring the food security of the republic.

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